

- GEOGRAPHY**
- █ Europe
 - █ Asia
 - █ N. America
 - █ S. America
 - █ Africa
 - █ Australia
 - unknown

- SUBSTRATE**
- █ clinical / hospital
 - █ food / feed
 - █ plant material
 - █ soil
 - █ other
 - unknown

